

1. Evaluation of RQ2

In this document, we describe the evaluation that assesses CAMA's capability to access the monitored data using a rich semantics method with the elements structured and defined through an ontology. To do so, we evaluate: (1) the consistency of the ontology, and (2) the reasoning capabilities of the ontology.

1.1 Evaluation of the consistency of the ontology

We evaluate that the knowledge represented in the ontology is consistent with its scope, i.e., that the ontology has enough information to answer the competence questions specified in Section 5. The expected results should demonstrate that the levels and modules, the extension of the ontology, and the conceptualization of the domain ontology are correct and consistent.

1.1.1 Protocol of the evaluation

To carry out this evaluation, we conduct the following tasks:

1. Translation of the following competence questions into the semantics of the SPARQL¹ query language:
 - What are the parameters that can be configured in a monitoring tool?
 - What kind of context information can be monitored by a monitoring tool?
 - What is the monitored data gathered by a specific monitoring tool?
 - What kind of response format is given by a certain configuration instance?
 - What instances of a monitoring tool or related configurations are activated?
 - What are the monitoring tools that can monitor a specific service or application (e.g., retrieve all the monitoring tools that can monitor the Twitter or the CPU of a system)?
2. Execution of the queries in the Protégé editor.

1.1.2 Results of the evaluation

The queries and the related results are specified in the following tables.

Table 1 shows a query to obtain all the monitoring tools that supervise the Twitter social network. As shown, two types of monitoring tools are retrieved, namely SocialMentionAPI and TwitterAPI. In Table 2, a variation of such a query is specified in order to obtain the monitors that supervise Facebook. As it can be seen, only the SocialMentionAPI has such a capability. This type of queries provide the list of monitoring tools capable of gathering data from the required entities. This is useful, for instance, to be able to replace a failing monitoring tool for another that is able to monitor the same entity.

Table 1. SPARQL query of Twitter monitoring tools

SPARQL query:
SELECT ?twittermonitors WHERE { ?twittermonitors <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt /SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#isMonitoringToolOf> <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ ComputationalEntity#Twitter>} twittermonitors
SocialMentionAPI
TwitterAPI

¹ <http://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>

Table 2. SPARQL query of Facebook monitoring tools

SPARQL query:
<pre>SELECT ?facebookmonitors WHERE { ?facebookmonitors <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ /SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#isMonitoringToolOf> <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ ComputationalEntity#Facebook>} facebookmonitors SocialMentionAPI</pre>

Table 3 shows a query that can retrieve all the configurable parameters in social networks monitoring tools. As it can be seen, four common parameters can be configured in monitoring tools for social networks. In a practical context, this provides which configuration parameters are necessary to start working with the required social networks monitoring tools.

Table 3. SPARQL query of parameters to configure a social network monitoring

SPARQL query:
<pre>SELECT ?confparameters WHERE { ?confparameters rdfs:domain <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#SocialNetworksMonitoringConfProf>} confparameters keywords timeslot confStatus outputFormat</pre>

Table 4 shows the monitored data that can be obtained from a social network monitoring tool, namely: idItem, link, timestamp, message and author. This information is useful to identify if the monitoring tool is capable of gathering the required contextual data.

Table 4. SPARQL query of data items of a monitoring tool

SPARQL query:
<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?dataitems WHERE { ?monitoreddata rdfs:domain <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#SocialNetworksMonitoredData> ?monitoreddata a owl:DatatypeProperty ?dataitems rdfs:domain <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#SocialNetworksDataItems> ?dataitems a owl:DatatypeProperty }</pre>
<pre>dataitems idItem link timestamp message author</pre>

Finally, Table 5 shows a detailed query required by the use cases to obtain, from the ontology, the monitoring tools of Twitter with all their information, i.e., configuration instances and their respective values that describe the inputs, outputs and configurations capabilities of Twitter monitoring tools. As it can be seen, there are two monitoring tools with confStatus true (i.e., active to supervise tweets). Each monitoring tool is related to a specific configuration profile that produces an output (e.g., author and message).

Table 5. SPARQL query of inputs/outputs of social networks monitoring tools

SPARQL query:					
<pre> SELECT ?monitor ?confStatus ?confProf ?keywords ?timeslot ?outputFormat ?monitoredData ?mdtimestamp ?dataitems ?author ?message WHERE { ?monitor <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#isMonitoringToolOf><http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/ threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ComputationalEntity#Twitter>. ?monitor <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#monitoringStatus>?confStatus . ?confProf <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#isConfigurationProfileOf>?monitor . ?confProf <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#keywords>?keywords . ?confProf <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#timeslot>?timeslot . ?confProf <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#outputFormat>?outputFormat . ?monitoredData <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#isProducedBy>?confProf . ?monitoredData <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#timestamp>?mdtimestamp . ?monitoredData <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#hasDataItems>?dataitems . ?dataitems <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#dataItemAuthor>?author . ?dataitems <http://gessi.lsi.upc.edu/threelevelcontextmodelling/ThreeLContextOnt/ SocialNetworksMonitoringTools#dataItemMessage>?message . } </pre>					
monitor	confStatus	confProf	keywords	timeslot	outputFormat
TwitterAPI	true	TwitterConfProf1	“Acme streaming service” AND quality	60	json
TwitterAPI	false	TwitterConfProf2	Acme AND quality	60	json
SocialMentionAPI	true	SocialMentionConfProf1	“Acme streaming service” AND quality	10	json
SocialMentionAPI	false	SocialMentionConfProf2	Acme AND quality	10	json
monitor	monitoredData	mdtimestamp	dataitems	author	message
TwitterAPI	TwitterAPIData1	2016-08-22 11:00	TwitterAPIDI1
TwitterAPI	TwitterAPIData2	2016-08-22 11:00	TwitterAPIDI2
SocialMentionAPI	SocialMentionData1	2016-08-20 10:45	SocialMentionDI1
SocialMentionAPI	SocialMentionData2	2016-08-20 10:45	SocialMentionDI2

The ontology of CAMA has mainly two roles: the role of responding the competence questions defined in subsection 1.1.1 through queries in SPARQL, and the role of reasoning for deducing new context knowledge. The first role can be carried out manually by humans and automatically by the algorithms and components of CAMA, whereas the second role can be executed only automatically by the internal rules, semantics and reasoner engines implemented in the ontology. For instance, the ontology can automatically detect if a monitoring tool of the SocialNetworksMonitoring class is not working properly (e.g., by detecting if the data items retrieved by a specific instance of the SocialNetworksMonitoringConfProf class are null), or if a reconfiguration of the keywords are needed because there are too many data items being collected.